

1 **Excellent interobserver agreement and steep learning curve for target**
2 **volume delineation for stereotactic arrhythmia radioablation (STAR)**
3 **using a commercial software**

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2 **Abstract (249)**

3 **Background and Aims**

4 Stereotactic arrhythmia radioablation (STAR) has emerged as bail-out treatment for ventricular
5 tachycardia (VT). Accurate, reproducible, and easy-to-use data transfer from electroanatomical mapping
6 (EAM) systems to radiotherapy planning CT is desirable. We aim to evaluate interobserver variability,
7 ease of use, and learning curve for EAM based target volume (CardTV-EP_{inv}) creation and transfer using
8 available software packages.

9 **Methods**

10 In patients considered for STAR, CardTV-EP_{inv} were created using ADAS and Slicer3D for workflow
11 comparison. Four CardTV-EP_{inv} (clinically targeted volume and three mock targets) were created by an
12 experienced operator and a 2nd-year medical student, based on endocardial EAM tags indicating VT
13 substrate location. CardTV-EP_{inv} sizes, Hausdorff distances (HD), and workflow duration were measured
14 to assess interobserver variability and learning curve.

15 **Results**

16 Agreement between CardTV-EP_{inv} was high using ADAS and Slicer3D workflows (HD 3.64 mm [2.7–4.5]).
17 ADAS workflow was faster and more robust (ADAS 26 min [24–29] vs. Slicer3D 65 min [61–70], $p < 0.001$;
18 system crashes: ADAS 0 vs. Slicer3D 7). In 20 patients (80% non-ischemic cardiomyopathy, LVEF
19 $35 \pm 14\%$), 80 CardTV-EP_{inv} were created using ADAS. CardTV-EP_{inv} size was similar for both observers
20 (11.8 ml [10.1–13.7] vs. 10.7 ml [9.6–11.8], $p = 0.17$), with high interobserver agreement (HD 1.68 mm
21 [1.45–1.96]; 95th percentile HD < 4.8 mm [3.5–5.7]). Linear regression showed a steep learning curve for
22 the student ($p = 0.01$).

23 **Conclusion**

24 CardTV-EP_{inv} creation showed excellent interobserver agreement and was faster and more robust using
25 ADAS than 3D slicer. The steep learning curve appears clinically relevant given the limited use of STAR
26 even in high-volume VT ablation centres.

27

28 **Keywords**

29 *Ventricular tachycardia*

1 *Ablation*

2 *Stereotactic arrhythmia radioablation*

3 *STAR*

4 *Interobserver variability in imaging and EAM merging*

5

6 **What's new?**

- 7
- 8 • This is the first study to evaluate the interobserver variability using open-source and
9 commercially available software packages for the transfer of CardTV-EP_{inv} to the planning
10 software for STAR.
 - 11 • Cardiac target volume creation is faster and more robust using the commercially available ADAS
12 compared to the open-source Slicer 3D software, with an excellent interobserver agreement for
13 both single- and multicenter EAM data, provided that recommended mapping standards are
14 applied.
 - 15 • The steep learning curve for inexperienced operators using ADAS is clinically relevant
16 considering the limited use of STAR, even in high volume VT ablation centers.
- 17

18 **Introduction**

19 Catheter ablation is one of the cornerstones in the treatment of scar-related ventricular tachycardia (VT)
20 (1-3). Outcomes are favorable for subendocardial or subepicardial substrate locations (1, 4-9). One
21 important limitation of the technique is the inability to reach deep intramural substrates, or those
22 protected by (epicardial) fat or calcifications. (10-13) Since its first report, stereotactic arrhythmia
23 radioablation (STAR) has emerged as a bail-out treatment option for patients with inaccessible
24 substrates. (14, 15)

25 STAR requires a close collaboration between electrophysiologists and radiation-oncologists. The
26 delineation of the inaccessible VT substrate (= cardiac target volume (CardTV)) is mainly based on
27 invasive endocardial or endo- and epicardial electroanatomic mapping (EAM) data provided by the
28 electrophysiologist, which needs to be extrapolated to a transmural volume, referred to as CardTV-EP_{inv}.
29 (16) 3D EAM data can be co-registered with a computed tomography (CT) scan and the delineated

1 CardTV-EP_{inv} can be transferred to the CT, which is used for radiation treatment planning. Different
2 workflows for CardTV-EP_{inv} delineation, co-registration and target data transfer have been proposed.
3 (17-21) Workflows have utilized either the open-source Slicer 3D software (3D to 3D registration) (17,
4 18, 22), or in-house developed software packages (2D to 3D registration) (22, 23) or the 17-segment
5 American Heart Association (AHA) model (20), while others have manually transferred EAM data to the
6 2D CT slices based on eyeballing. (19, 24) The quality of the available 3D EAM data has been shown to
7 impact the interobserver agreement for the transferred CardTV-EP_{inv}. (18, 21)

8 Since the use of STAR remains limited, even in high volume VT ablation center with > 50 complex VT
9 ablations per year, (2) there is a need for an accurate, reproducible and robust data transfer workflow,
10 that is easy to learn and/or already used by electrophysiologists. The ADAS 3D anatomy segmentation
11 tool is a commercially available software package (ADAS 3D SL, Spain), which is used as a (pre-
12)procedural image integration tool, in both atrial and ventricular ablations. (25) The use of ADAS in
13 CardTV-EP_{inv} delineation has been only case-reported. (26) Slicer 3D workflow uses open-source
14 software and has been reported as a method of 3D-to-3D transfer of mapping data to CT with a high
15 interobserver agreement. (17, 21, 22, 27)

16 The aims of this study are threefold: to evaluate (1) the intraobserver variability, ease of use and
17 workflow duration for available software packages; (2) the interobserver agreement for CardTV-EP_{inv}
18 creation and transfer using (i) single center data and (ii) multicenter data of STAR-treated patients from
19 the STOPSTORM.eu consortium (28); and (3) the learning curve for CardTV-EP_{inv} creation and transfer.

20 **Methods**

21 ***Patient population***

22 The study population consisted of patients who underwent EAM and catheter ablation for VT using the
23 CARTO mapping system (Biosense Webster Inc., California, USA) and were considered potential
24 candidates for STAR bail-out therapy based on the substrate properties known to be difficult to control
25 with ablation. All patients were identified as potential candidates for STAR during the ablation
26 procedure, based on the acute procedural outcome (partial procedural success, failure to completely
27 eliminate the VT substrate). In each patient the potential target area was demarcated on the EAM after
28 the procedure. Fortunately, not all patients needed STAR as bail-out therapy after ablation. Since the
29 planning-CT is made immediately prior to radiation, only the patients who underwent STAR had a
30 planning-CT available. Patients were treated at the Leiden University Medical Center (LUMC), Leiden,

1 the Netherlands, the Lausanne University Hospital (CHUV), Lausanne, Switzerland, the Maastricht
2 University Medical Center (MUMC+)/Maastricht, Maastricht, the Netherlands, or the Institute for Clinical
3 and Experimental Medicine (IKEM), Prague/University Hospital of Ostrava, Ostrava, Czech Republic
4 between January 2018 and March 2024. Supplemental Figure S1 visualizes the patient cohorts.

5 ***CT acquisition***

6 All ECG-gated CT-scan with contrast were acquired in diastole and inspiration breath-hold. The slice
7 thickness of the ECG-gated CT scans was 0.5 mm. Radiotherapy 3D contrast CTs and 4D respiratory-
8 gated CTs were acquired in free breathing (in the same frame of reference). Target delineations were
9 expanded to account for respiratory motion using the 4D CT phases. Radiotherapy treatment planning
10 was performed on 3D CT (n=7), or 4D CT average reconstruction (n=4). The slice thickness and spacing
11 between slices was 2 mm for all cases, and the in-plane pixel spacing was 1 ± 0.1 mm in left-right and
12 anterior-posterior direction for all cases.

13

14 ***Workflow for cardiac target volume creation***

15 Target areas were indicated on the (endocardial) surface of the EAM in Carto using pre-defined tags that
16 encircle the area of the inaccessible substrate, defined as area of interest (AOI). All EAM data were
17 exported from the Carto system for offline use.

18 The workflow for creating the CardTV-EP_{inv} using Slicer 3D has been described previously. (21) Briefly,
19 the endocardial EAM surface data in polygon .mesh data and the tags created on the EAM were
20 imported in Slicer 3D, where the cardiac anatomy was segmented from the CT scan. Using custom
21 Python plugins, the EAM points were projected on the 3D anatomy. Then, using the projected points on
22 the LV surface, the CardTV-EP_{inv} was determined by creating perpendicular lines from the endocardial
23 surface to the epicardial surface. These lines were then connected to form one volume (CardTV-EP_{inv})
24 based on the 2D target area demarcated by the projected EAM points.

25 Using ADAS, the cardiac anatomy (aorta, left ventricle (LV), left main coronary artery, right ventricle (RV)
26 and pulmonary artery (PA) was extracted from the cardiac CT and projected as a 3D model using the
27 Heart Anatomy Extraction tool. This was done with either the auto-segmentation tool or, when auto-
28 segmentation did not yield satisfactory results, for example, due to artifacts from cardiac implantable
29 devices, threshold segmentation was used. Anatomical structure contours were verified to be correct

1 with the 2D slices in all three axes. The left ventricular wall thickness was determined by manually
2 contouring the endo- and epicardial surface. The space between the contours (the LV wall) was
3 converted into a 3D structure. After importing the EAM data into ADAS, the 3D mapping data was
4 merged with the 3D CT model using all available EAM structures and distinct landmarks
5 (LV/RV/aorta/left main coronary/pulmonary artery etc.) by manually translating and rotating the
6 structures and aligning the landmark points where available. The target area tags were projected on the
7 3D LV endocardial surface. In ADAS, EAM points were automatically projected to the closest endocardial
8 contour. In the Slicer 3D workflow, this option is not available. Using the segment creation tool in ADAS
9 3D, the AOI was converted by the operator into a transmural 3D volume (CardTV-EP_{inv}) in the 3D LV wall.
10 This was done by first connecting the tags on the endocardial surface and then creating perpendicular
11 lines from the endocardial circle to the closest epicardial border, or the RV endocardial contours for
12 septal sites. See supplementary material for a detailed workflow description. The CardTV-EP_{inv} was
13 created on both the cardiac (diastolic ECG-gated) CT-scan and the radiation-oncology (non-ECG-gated)
14 planning CT-scan (where available) to determine agreement between volumes using these different CT
15 acquisition sequences.

16 In addition to the clinical AOI, three remote areas of a potentially inaccessible VT substrate location
17 were indicated by tags on a separate map to create mock CardTV-EP_{inv} to determine the influence of
18 substrate location on interobserver variability. These areas were located in basal anterior segments (LV
19 summit region, AHA segment 1), mid-septal (AHA segments 8 & 9), mid-lateral (AHA segments 11 & 12)
20 and apico-inferior (AHA segment 15) segments representing common substrate locations in patients
21 undergoing STAR. (19, 21, 24, 29)

22 The time needed for each step and the performance of the software packages (e.g. software crashes)
23 were noted.

24

25 ***Intraobserver variability, ease of use and workflow time for available software packages***

26 For the evaluation of the intraobserver variability and ease of use, both workflows were followed by
27 operator #1 (RR) highly experienced with both software packages. The patients used for this analysis
28 consisted of the LUMC patients treated by STAR, with only the clinical target volume analyzed, without
29 mock volumes. The same target area indicated by the predefined tags on the 3D EAM was used to
30 create CardTV-EP_{inv}. The number of software crashes during the creation of the CardTV-EP_{inv} was

1 registered. A software crash was defined as a non-intended shutdown of the software program with
2 consequential data loss. The time lost due to a software crash was not included in the total workflow
3 time.

4 The created CardTV-EP_{inv} were exported from ADAS and Slicer 3D in .vtk format and imported in Slicer
5 3D for comparison. Using a built-in tool in Slicer 3D (Segment Comparison), the volumes of the CardTV-
6 EP_{inv} and the mean- and 95% Hausdorff distance (HD) between each pair of CardTV-EP_{inv} were
7 determined. The HD is the greatest of all distances from a point of one surface to a point on the co-
8 registered surface. The HD was calculated for each outer surface point on the created volumes (21). The
9 mean HD is defined as the average of all distances and the 95th percentile of the ordered
10 distance (95% of all points are within this distance). (21)

11

12 ***Interobserver agreement for CardTV-EP_{inv} creation and transfer using (i) single center data and (ii)***
13 ***multicenter data of STAR-treated patients from the STOPSTORM.eu consortium***

14 To evaluate the interobserver variability of CardTV-EP_{inv} creation and transfer using high quality data as
15 previously defined, (21) datasets from a single high-volume center (LUMC) were used. This patient
16 cohort consisted of all patients treated for VT by ablation in the LUMC (n=20) and who were considered
17 potential candidates for STAR. Fortunately, not all patients required STAR after ablation. For each case,
18 mapping data of at least 3 structures and/or landmarks and ECG-gated CT-scans with contrast were
19 available. In addition to the clinical target area, three additional mock areas were created to determine
20 the influence of the substrate location on the interobserver agreement.

21 To determine the potential impact of multicenter data (e.g. variation in mapping density, variation in
22 number and type of structures/landmarks mapped) on the interobserver variability, datasets from four
23 centers involved in the European prospective STOPSTORM.eu consortium were used. (28) All included
24 patients were considered candidates for STAR treatment and had the clinical target area indicated on
25 the 3D EAM. The single center patients who underwent STAR after ablation (n=7) were also included in
26 the multicenter data analysis. The clinically treated CardTV-EP_{inv} created by observer #1 in the
27 intraobserver agreement analysis (ADAS/Slicer comparison) were re-used in the multicenter
28 (ADAS/ADAS) comparison.

1 Two observers (observer #1, highly experienced in creating CardTV-EP and observer #2 (SC)
2 inexperienced) performed the entire workflow separately using ADAS. The volumes of the CardTV-EP
3 and the mean- and 95% HD between each pair of CardTV-EP were determined.

4 To determine the potential variability in volumes using an ECG-gated CT or a non-gated radiotherapy
5 planning CT, the clinical CardTV-EP_{inv} was created using ADAS on both CT scans.

6 The analysis included four steps of potential interobserver variability in the transfer of EAM data to the
7 CT scan:

- 8 1) Segmentation of the 3D anatomy from the 2D CT slices
- 9 2) Co-registration of the EAM data with the 3D CT anatomy
- 10 3) Location of the EAM target area tags on the CT endocardial surface when automatic projection
11 of the EAM points to the endocardial surface is not available (i.e. in the Slicer3D workflow).
- 12 4) Creation of the final CardTV-EP_{inv} including the direction of transmural (e.g. at the RV
13 insertion) and the involvement of adjacent structures (e.g. papillary muscles).

14 ***Learning curve for an inexperienced observer***

15 To determine the learning curve of an inexperienced observer, the time needed for the segmentation of
16 the anatomy, the co-registration of EAM data with the CT anatomy and for the creation of the CardTV-
17 EP_{inv} was measured. The inexperienced observer, a medical student without any prior experience with
18 3D mapping data, cardiac CT (CCT) reading and the use of the software package, received a written
19 description of the workflow and a one-time demonstration.

20 ***Statistical analysis***

21 Continuous variables are reported as median with interquartile range (IQR) or mean \pm standard
22 deviation, when appropriate. Data were compared using the student's t-test, Mann-Whitney U test, and
23 one-way ANOVA, when appropriate. Linear regression models were calculated using ANOVA. Categorical
24 variables were compared with the Chi-squared test and Fisher's exact test, when appropriate. P-values
25 below 0.05 were considered statistically significant. All statistical analyses were performed in SPSS
26 version 27.0 (IBM Corporation, Armonk, New York).

27

28

1 **Ethical approval**

2 All used patient data was (pseudo)anonymized: imaging series and EAM were named after the center,
3 and a follow-number was given per patient (e.g. LUMC_1 etc.). Patient baseline characteristics data was
4 exported by the treating physician and coded in a similar manner. Ethical approval for data usage was
5 obtained through the local ethical committee (non-WMO, METc Leiden University, Leiden, the
6 Netherlands, reference W22_193 # 22.241) for the single center patients and through the
7 STOPSTORM.eu ethical approval for the multicenter patients (non-WMO, Amsterdam UMC, Amsterdam,
8 the Netherlands, reference W22_193 # 22.241).

9

10 **Results**

11 ***Patient population***

12 A total of 32 patients from four centers were included (median age 65 years [IQR 57 – 74], 91% male,
13 70% non-ischemic cardiomyopathy (NICM), median LVEF 33% [IQR 26 – 46], median 2 [IQR 1 – 3] prior
14 VT ablations). In 20/32 patients, an ECG-gated CT scan was available and in 19/32 a non-gated planning
15 CT was also available. Among all scans, left ventricular contrast was present in 31/32 patients. In 16/32
16 patients, both LV and RV contrast was present. All patients had an LV EAM available, and in 24/32
17 patients at least three structures/landmarks were mapped (including LV, RV, aorta, pulmonary artery,
18 left atrium, ostium of the left main coronary artery). For the 19 patients with an available radiotherapy
19 planning CT and CardTV-EP_{inv} demarcated by endocardial tags, the target areas were lateral (6), septal
20 (6), anterior/apical (3), basal anterior (2), and inferior (2). Nineteen of the 32 patients were included in
21 the STOPSTORM.eu registry. See Table 1 for details.

22 ***Intraobserver variability, ease of use and workflow time for available software packages***

23 Datasets of seven patients (67±12 years, 4 NICM, median LVEF 26% (range 19 – 42), median 3 prior
24 ablation (range 1-6)) who underwent STAR at the LUMC were processed by the experienced operator
25 using ADAS and Slicer 3D. All patients had available EAM data of the endocardial LV, the aorta, and the
26 position of the LM. RV endocardial mapping was performed in 4/7. All patients had ECG-gated cardiac
27 CT with contrast. In all patients the clinical AOI was indicated by tags and was located at the (basal)
28 septum (n=2), the basal anterior (n=1), lateral (n=2) and apical (n=2) LV.

1 The CardTV-EP_{inv} created in Slicer 3D were larger compared to those created in ADAS (median 50.2 ml
2 [IQR 33.4 – 84.8] vs. 36.0 ml [IQR 14.4 – 50.3], median volume difference 21.8 ml [IQR 3.4 – 28.9],
3 $p < 0.05$). The average HD distance between volumes was 3.6 mm [2.7 – 4.5] and the 95th percentile
4 distance was 9.0 mm [6.72 [IQR 6.7 – 13.0]]. The differences in volume size in the Slicer 3D workflow
5 were explained by an expansion of the volume into the blood pool for septal substrates and into the
6 blood pool and extra-cardiac structures for the basal, lateral and inferior target areas. In all cases, the
7 entire volume created in ADAS was overlapped by the volume created in Slicer3D. See examples in
8 Supplementary figure S3. Duration of the Slicer 3D workflow was significantly longer than that with
9 ADAS (65 [IQR 61 – 70] vs 26 [24 – 29] minutes respectively, $p < 0.001$). Seven total software crashes
10 occurred in four cases while using the Slicer 3D workflow but none with the ADAS workflow. Table 2
11 provides the details of the workflow comparison. Considering the longer workflow duration and the high
12 number of software crashes using Slicer 3D, the interobserver variability analysis for single and
13 multicenter data was only performed with ADAS.

14 15 ***Interobserver agreement for CardTV-EP creation and transfer using single center LUMC data***

16 Datasets of twenty patients who underwent work-up for STAR in the LUMC were used (median age 65
17 years [IQR 57 – 75], 95% male, median LVEF, 32% [IQR 26 – 44%], 80% NICM, median number of
18 ablations, 1 [IQR 1 – 3]). For reference, from January 2018 to March 2024, a total of 964 ventricular
19 ablations were performed. All included study patients ($n=20$) had undergone at least LV endocardial and
20 aorta mapping. In 19 (95%) patients, the LM was tagged during the procedure for image registration.
21 Eleven (55%) patients underwent additional RV and PA mapping. In all patients an ECG-gated CT with LV
22 contrast was present, and in 11/20 patients LV and RV contrast was available. In addition, a planning CT
23 was available in seven patients. See Table 1 for details. The clinical AOI and additional three mock areas
24 per patient were indicated on the 3D EAM and CardTV-EP_{inv} were created and transferred independently
25 by both observers on the ECG-gated CT-scan. In one patient only two additional mock areas were
26 created because the mapping density in the basal anterior region was not sufficient to create an AOI.

27 A total of 79 CardTV-EP were compared. There was no statistically significant difference between the
28 overall volume sizes between observers (11.8 ml [IQR 10.1 – 13.7] for observer #1 vs. 10.7 ml [IQR 9.6 –
29 11.8] for observer #2 (p -value: 0.17)). Only for the mid-septal location, the volume size was statistically

1 different between both observers (13 ml [IQR 9 – 16] vs. 10 ml [IQR 7 – 15], p-value 0.01). See Table 3
2 for details.

3 The average HD distance between all volumes created by the two observers was only 1.7 mm [IQR 1.5 –
4 2.0] and the 95th percentile distance was 4.8 mm [IQR 3.5 – 5.7]. Agreement was highest for the apico-
5 inferior volumes (average HD distance 1.5 mm [1.0 – 1.8]), and lowest for mid-septal volumes (average
6 HD distance 1.8 mm [IQR 1.2 – 2.7] See Table 3 for details.

7 The presence of left-sided or left- and right-sided contrast did not influence the interobserver
8 agreement: the average distance was 1.9 mm [IQR 1.4 – 2.1] in patients with only left-sided contrast and
9 1.7 mm [IQR 1.4 – 1.9] in patients with left- and right-sided contrast (p-value: 0.552).

10 From six patients, the CardTV-EP_{inv} were created and transferred using both the ECG-gated CT and the
11 non-gated radiotherapy planning CT. The median difference between volumes was 4.0 ml [IQR 2.5 –
12 9.5], where the non-gated scan always showed the larger of the two volumes (median volume size ECG-
13 gated scan, 34 [IQR 17 – 53] versus 39 ml [IQR 29 – 59] in non-gated scan). The average HD distance
14 between volumes was 2.9 mm [IQR 2.3 – 3.5].

15

16 ***Interobserver agreement for CardTV-EP creation and transfer using multicenter data of STAR-treated*** 17 ***patients from the STOPSTORM.eu consortium***

18 Data of 19 patients (median age 65 years [IQR 59 – 73], 90% male, 47% NICM, median LVEF 32% [IQR 26
19 – 44], median 2 prior VT ablations [IQR 2 – 4]) from 4 different centers (LUMC 7, CHUV 6, IKEM 3, MUMC
20 3) who were prospectively included in the STOPSTORM.eu registry and treated with STAR were
21 processed by the two observers (table 1). In all patients the clinical CardTV-EP_{inv} was created,
22 transferred and treated. The quality of the EAM data (number of chambers/landmarks, completeness of
23 surface mapping, point density) varied between cases. Left ventricular contrast was present in all but
24 one patient (95%) and both LV and RV contrast was present in 10 patients (53%). The median difference
25 in volume sizes between observers was 2.1 ml [IQR 1.1 – 5.2]. HD distance between volumes was a
26 median 1.8 mm [IQR 1.5 – 2.7] and the 95th percentile distance was 5.4 mm [IQR 3.9 – 7.9]. In 11/19
27 patients, a minimum of three chambers/landmarks was mapped, and in 11/11 LV or LV/RV contrast was
28 given. The median HD distance and 95th percentile distance in these patients was significantly smaller
29 compared to patients with less than three chambers/landmarks mapped (median distance 1.6 mm [IQR

1 1.3 – 2.0] vs. 2.6 mm [IQR 1.8 – 4.1]; 95th percentile distance 4.1 mm [IQR 3.6 – 5.7] vs. 7.3 mm [IQR 5.3
2 – 11.3], both $P < 0.05$). See Table 4 and Supplementary Table 5 for details.

3

4 ***Learning curve for the workflow***

5 Following the one-time demonstration case using the written workflow instruction, the duration of the
6 workflow for the inexperienced observer decreased significantly for consecutive treated patients: for
7 the first five cases, observer #2 needed a median of 134 minutes [IQR 98 – 177] to complete the
8 workflow, which dropped down to a median of 68 minutes [IQR 65 – 80] for the next fifteen (p-
9 value < 0.001). Linear regression analysis showed a statistically significant downward trend in workflow
10 completion time for observer #2 (R^2 0.534, p-value < 0.001). The time needed by observer #1 to
11 complete the workflow remained stable throughout the study (mean 37 ± 7 min (R^2 : 0.06, p-value =
12 0.155). See Figure 1 and Supplementary Table S1 for details.

13 The agreement between observers also improved over time. For the first five cases, the HD between
14 volumes was 2.2 mm [IQR 1.7 – 3.0] and 1.7 mm [IQR 1.3 – 1.9] for the following consecutive cases (p-
15 value = 0.01). Similarly, the 95% percentile HD was 6.0 mm [IQR 4.6 – 8.5] for the first five cases and 5.0
16 mm [IQR 3.5 – 5.3] for the next fifteen cases (p-value = 0.003). Linear regression analysis showed
17 improvement over time for both average HD and 95th percentile HD between observers (average HD: R^2 :
18 0.355, p-value 0.01; 95th percentile distance: R^2 : 0.271, p-value 0.02). For the last fifteen cases, 14/15
19 (93%) patients had an average HD distance between volumes of < 2.0 mm. See Table S1, Supplementary
20 Figures S2 and S3 for details.

21

22 **Discussion**

23 This study is the first to systematically analyze the accuracy, ease of use and workflow duration for
24 CardTV-EP_{inv} delineation for STAR using currently available software packages for single center, mapping
25 data acquired according to current recommendations (16) (i.e. more than three structures mapped) and
26 for multicenter datasets (with varying number of structures mapped) of STAR-treated patients from the
27 STOPSTORM.eu registry.

28 The main findings of the study can be summarized as follows:

1 1) Both software packages, Slicer 3D and ADAS, allow for CardTV-EP_{inv} creation with complete overlap of
2 the smaller volume, but resulting in larger volumes using Slicer 3D. Even if performed by an experienced
3 operator, the Slicer 3D workflow is more time-consuming and vulnerable to software crashes.

4 2) For high quality EAM data acquired according to current recommendations (16) (e.g. sufficient
5 mapping density, number and type of chambers/landmarks mapped) the interobserver agreement using
6 the ADAS workflow is excellent with an HD between volumes of only 1.7 mm.

7 The high interobserver agreement could be achieved with the ADAS workflow by an inexperienced
8 observer after only five cases, with a shorter workflow duration than that of Slicer 3D by an experienced
9 operator.

10 3) For unselected multicenter data from the prospective STOPSTORM.eu registry the interobserver
11 agreement was also high (average distance 2.0 mm) using the ADAS workflow, but significantly more
12 accurate for cases with more than three structures mapped.

13 These findings suggest that ADAS workflow adequately addresses the four steps of potential
14 interobserver variability, resulting in high interobserver agreement, provided that sufficient structures
15 are mapped as advised by the recent consensus document. (16)

16

17 ***Existing workflows for CardTV-EP_{inv} creation***

18 Delineation of the CardTV-EP_{inv} which is based on invasive endocardial or endo- and epicardial EAM data
19 indicated by the electrophysiologist on a surface and which needs to be extrapolated to a transmural
20 volume and its transfer to the planning CT scan remains a manual task. Different workflows have been
21 proposed using in-house-developed software and/or open-source software packages (17, 20, 21, 30).

22 Two-dimensional free-hand target delineation using eyeballing has proven to be inconsistent and poorly
23 reproducible, resulting in large variation of CardTV-EPs. (31) As invasive mapping data and cardiac CT
24 data both provide 3D co-ordinates of anatomical structures and AOI, the advantages of workflows that
25 utilize 3D to 3D registration are obvious. Of note, as of now, none of these software packages are CE-
26 marked (32).

27 Two single center studies have analyzed the Slicer 3D workflow (open-source software) for
28 interobserver variability for steps 1-3 (see Method section) of the data transfer to the radiotherapy
29 planning CT. (17, 21, 27). Both studies reported a high interobserver agreement after registration of the

1 segmented anatomy of either the 3D location of the endocardial EAM tags without projection, or the 2D
2 area created by connecting these non-projected tags. However, high agreement between endocardial
3 tag locations or a fixed 2D area may not reflect agreement in 3D target volumes and location.
4 Differences in wall thickness estimation, direction of transmural in particular at the RV/LV insertion
5 areas or at papillary muscle sites may influence the final volumes.

6

7 ***Comparison between ADAS and Slicer 3D workflows***

8 The ADAS 3D anatomy segmentation tool is a commercially available software package, which is used as
9 a (pre-)procedural image integration tool for both atrial and ventricular ablations. To the best of our
10 knowledge there are no studies on the interobserver agreement for CardTV-EP_{inv} delineation using
11 ADAS. The workflow for CardTV-EP_{inv} delineation using ADAS has been only case-reported. (26)

12 If performed by an experienced observer, the agreement on CardTV-EP_{inv} location created in ADAS and
13 Slicer 3D was comparable to the previously reported interobserver agreement on target volume location
14 using Slicer 3D (21). Of note, volumes created in Slicer 3D were larger than volumes created in ADAS,
15 which explains the difference in HD despite a very good visual overlap of the volumes. The larger
16 volumes can be explained by the workflow steps to create transmural volumes. In ADAS, the LV and RV
17 endo- and epicardial contours are segmented separately, resulting in a 3D shell with fixed boundaries in
18 which the CardTV-EP_{inv} can be created. In Slicer 3D, this function does not exist, which might lead to the
19 extension of the volume towards the epicardium for free wall targets and the blood pool for septal
20 targets and requiring target volume editing by the radiation-oncologist. Additionally, in ADAS, the option
21 to first connect all pre-defined tags to encircle the AOI can be done in 3D, directly on the endocardial
22 surface. In Slicer 3D, there are no such options. This may result in the creation of a larger CardTV-EP_{inv}
23 than intended. See Supplementary Figure S4 for examples. The limited inaccuracy in volume
24 determination using Slicer 3D is also reflected by the differences between observers in volumes
25 delineation in a previous study, where one observer created significantly larger volumes than the other
26 (21). In the current study, no such volume differences occurred with ADAS. Whether the larger CardTV-
27 EP_{inv} volumes as created by Slicer 3D would impact safety or efficiency of STAR needs further
28 investigation. When defining the definitive target for STAR editing of the CardTV-EP_{inv} volume to obvious
29 non-target areas (e.g. blood pool or extracardiac) as described in the International Committee for
30 Radiological Units report 83 is therefore warranted. (33)

1 Prior studies did not report on workflow duration, ease of use, or software crashes using Slicer
2 3D, which is important for clinical applications. The Slicer 3D workflow is open-source and available
3 without costs. However, compatibility with software updates in the mapping systems and software
4 stability are not guaranteed. Programming skills in Python are required to convert the data exported
5 from the mapping system to the input data for Slicer 3D. The Slicer 3D software, with all necessary
6 plugins installed, was prone to software crashes and freezes in our study, demonstrated by the high
7 number of crashes leading to data loss in seven instances spread over four cases, whereas no software
8 crash was observed with ADAS.

9 From a radiotherapy planning perspective, ADAS can output RTSTRUCT files, which is considered
10 an industry DICOM standard. As of now, the Slicer 3D workflow only outputs CT-scans with whitened out
11 voxels containing the target area. For the radiotherapy planning, this is less desirable since manual
12 overriding of the DICOM data is necessary.

14 **Influence of the quality of 3D mapping data**

15 Acquisition of mapping data is at the discretion of the operator and may vary across centres. Patients
16 referred for STAR are refractory to conventional treatment by definition. The mapping data are often
17 obtained during a failed ablation, and patients may be electrical unstable which may impact the quality
18 of data. Therefore, we have evaluated the interobserver agreement for CardTV-EP_{inv} delineation in
19 patients treated at a single centre where a minimum of three chambers/landmarks were mapped in
20 almost all patients, and in patients included in the prospective STOPSTORM.eu registry. According to the
21 recent clinical consensus statement, it is advised to obtain detailed EAM covering the surface of the
22 chamber of interest with anatomical marking of at least three chambers/landmarks in preparation of
23 CardTV-EP_{inv} whenever possible. (16) This advice is based on one prior study using the Slicer 3D
24 workflow. (21) In the single centre data cohort of this study, all patients met these requirements and the
25 interobserver agreement for CardTV-EP_{inv} in this cohort was high. In the multicentre data, 24/32 patients
26 met the advised mapping requirements. The high interobserver agreement using the ADAS workflow
27 was confirmed for multicentre data with excellent results if at least three structures have been mapped,
28 further supporting the advice of the clinical consensus statement.

29
30

1 ***Influence of substrate location on observer agreement***

2 To analyze the effect of substrate locations on the interobserver variability in the creation of the STAR
3 volumes, mock targets were created to simulate prevalent substrate locations in patients referred for
4 STAR. In a previous study, the lateral wall substrates had the highest interobserver variability, causing
5 authors to suggest that margins might need to be increased when targeting substrates in this location.
6 (21) In our study, all target locations performed similarly, with only the mid-septal region having
7 statistically significant differences in volume size. The increased HD in the mid-septal volumes can be
8 explained by the difference in size between the volumes. One possible explanation for the size
9 difference may be the absence of right-sided contrast, which hampers the accurate delineation of the
10 RV septal border. Since extension of the volume towards the RV side of the septum affects mainly the
11 blood-pool this may have no consequences for the radiation planning and on organs at risk. However,
12 the location of the moderator band needs to be considered. For the lateral and apico-inferior substrate
13 locations, however, this might have consequences for the radiation planning, because of the proximity
14 of organs-at-risk such as the stomach, bowels and lungs.

15 ***Planning CT-scan versus ECG-gated CT scan***

16 Planning volumes for STAR are created on the radiotherapy planning CT-scans. To determine the
17 differences in volumes between the two scans, the volumes were created on both the ECG-gated scan
18 and the planning CT-scan. The volumes created on ECG-gated CT-scans were smaller than those created
19 on planning CT scans. However, differences were small with a median of 4 ml between volumes, for a
20 median volume of 39 ml. In all but one patient, the smaller volumes based on the ECG-gated CT were
21 completely included in the larger planning CT-scan volumes. The difference in volume may be explained
22 by the lack of ECG-triggering. The contours of the endo- and epicardium are less sharply demarcated
23 due to the acquisition during systole and diastole, which in turn suggests a larger myocardial volume
24 than when the CT-slices are only created during diastole. Additionally, the slice thickness is four times
25 higher and pixel spacing doubled in the planning-CTs compared to the ECG-gated CT-scan.

26 ***Learning curve for the ADAS workflow***

27 By including one highly experienced observer and one inexperienced observer, this study can determine
28 the learning curve of new users. The second observer had no experience in creating CardTV-EP_{inv} for
29 STAR and in the use of ADAS anatomy segmentation. Thus, the outcomes for workflow duration and
30 observer agreement improvement reflect a real-world learning scenario showing that a new user can

1 accurately and reliably create CardTV-EP_{inv} after a low number of cases. Our study showed clear
2 improvement of workflow duration and interobserver agreement. After five cases, almost all cases had
3 an average distance shift between volumes below 2mm. This robustness of the workflow may lead to
4 improved patient outcomes because of the high accuracy of data transfer from the mapping system to
5 the planning CT. The time needed for a case dropped significantly after five cases, from a median of 134
6 minutes for the first five to a median of 68 minutes for the last fifteen. The observer agreement and
7 workflow duration improvement after only five cases is highly relevant since the use of STAR for
8 refractory VT is still limited, even in high volume VT ablation centers. Online tutorials and expert case
9 reviews (through e.g. STOSTORM.eu) may facilitate implementation of the workflow in clinical practice.

10

11 **Limitations**

12 This study sought to overcome limitations of prior studies by increasing the case numbers and adding
13 one more substrate location to the analysis. The median volume of the mock CardTV-EP_{inv} was smaller
14 than those reported in previous clinical cases. However, we feel that this does not impact the
15 reproducibility of the high interobserver variability, since the smaller the volumes, the less likely it is that
16 random variance causes volume overlap. Also, the data used for this study is obtained from high-volume
17 VT centers, which may limit the generalizability of the results.

18

19 **Conclusion**

20 Cardiac target volume creation was faster and more robust using ADAS compared to the custom Slicer
21 3D software, with an excellent interobserver agreement in both single- and multicenter data, provided
22 that recommended mapping standards are applied. There was a steep learning curve for inexperienced
23 operators using ADAS, which may be relevant, considering the limited use of STAR, even in high volume
24 VT ablation centers.

25

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2 / ADAS 3D Medical had no involvement in the study design, patient selection, data analysis,
3 interpretation of results, or any other aspect of this manuscript.

4 ***Data availability statement***

5 The data underlying this article will be shared upon reasonable request to the corresponding author.

ACCEPTED MANUSCRIPT

1 Graphical abstract / central illustration

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1 Tables and figures

2 Table 1: Patient characteristics, imaging protocols and electroanatomical mapping structures

	All patients N=32	Single center patients N=20	Multicenter patients N=19*
Patient characteristics			
<i>Age, years</i>	65 [57 – 74]	65 [57 – 75]	65 [56 – 73]
<i>Male</i>	29 (91)	19 (95)	17 (90)
<i>NICM</i>	22 (70)	16 (80)	9 (47)
<i>LVEF, %</i>	33 [26 – 46]	32 [26 – 44]	32 [24 – 46]
<i>Prior VT ablations</i>	2 [1 – 3]	1 [1 – 3]	3 [2 – 4]
Imaging			
<i>LV contrast</i>	15 (47)	9 (45)	8 (42)
<i>LV+RV contrast</i>	16 (50)	11 (55)	10 (53)
<i>No contrast</i>	1 (3)	0 (0)	1 (5)
<i>ECG-gated CT</i>	20 (63)	20 (100)	7 (37)
<i>Non-gated planning CT</i>	19 (59)	7 (35)	19 (100)
EAM structures			
<i>Left ventricle</i>	32 (100)	20 (100)	19 (100)
<i>Aorta</i>	24 (75)	20 (100)	11 (58)
<i>Right ventricle</i>	16 (50)	11 (55)	10 (53)
<i>Left main coronary artery</i>	19 (59)	19 (95)	7 (37)
<i>Pulmonary artery</i>	10 (31)	8 (40)	6 (32)
<i>Left atrium</i>	4 (13)	0 (0)	4 (21)
<i>Three or more structures mapped</i>	24 (75)	20 (100)	11 (53)

CT, computed tomography; EAM, electroanatomical map; ECG, electrocardiogram; LV, left ventricle; LVEF, left-ventricular ejection fraction; NICM, non-ischemic cardiomyopathy; RV, right ventricle; VT, ventricular tachycardia. Numbers are provided as N (%) and median [IQR].

*including 7 LUMC patients (single center)

1

2 **Table 2: Comparison between ADAS and Slicer 3D workflow (experienced operator)**

CardTV-EP volumes	ADAS N=7	Slicer 3D N=7	P-value
<i>Volume, ml</i>	36.0 [14.4 – 50.3]	50.2 [33.4 – 84.8]	0.01
<i>Difference in volumes, ml [IQR]</i>	21.8 [IQR 3.4 – 28.9]		0.002
<i>Average HD, mm</i>	3.6 [2.7 – 4.5]		
<i>95% HD, mm</i>	9.0 [6.7 – 13.0]		
Workflow duration			
<i>Total duration, min</i>	26 [24 – 29]	65 [61 – 70]	<0.001
<i>Anatomy segmentation, min</i>	12 [10 – 12]	38 [35 – 40]	<0.001
<i>EAM and anatomy merge, min [IQR]</i>	8 [7 – 9]	13 [12 – 15]	0.002
<i>Target drawing, min</i>	6 [5 – 7]	15 [11 – 16]	<0.001
Number of software crashes	0	7	0.05

3

EAM, electroanatomical map; min, minutes; ml, milliliter; mm, millimeter; HD, Hausdorff distance. All values are reported in median [IQR].

1 **Table 3: Interobserver comparison using ADAS for single center data**

CardTV-EP location	Observer 1	Observer 2	P-value
All CardTV-EP_{inv} (n=79)			
<i>Volume, ml</i>	11.8 [10.1 – 13.7]	10.7 [9.6 – 11.8]	0.17
<i>Difference in volume, ml</i>	1.2 [1.1 – 1.5]		
<i>Average HD, mm</i>	1.7 [1.5 – 2.0]		
<i>95% HD, mm</i>	4.8 [3.5 – 5.7]		
Basal anterior (n=19)			
<i>Volume, ml</i>	8.5 [6.8 – 14.6]	8.3 [7.4 – 12.2]	0.36
<i>Average HD, mm</i>	1.6 [1.2 – 2.1]		
<i>95% HD, mm</i>	4.2 [3.3 – 6.5]		
Apico-inferior (n=20)			
<i>Volume, ml</i>	13.1 [10.0 – 18.2]	12.6 [8.3 – 17.5]	0.10
<i>Average HD, mm</i>	1.5 [1.0 – 1.8]		
<i>95% HD, mm</i>	4.2 [3.0 – 5.0]		
Mid-septal (n=20)			
<i>Volume, ml</i>	12.6 [9.3 – 16.3]	9.6 [7.4 – 15.1]	0.01
<i>Average HD, mm</i>	1.8 [1.2 – 2.7]		
<i>95% HD, mm</i>	5.6 [3.6 – 7.3]		
Mid-lateral (n=20)			
<i>Volume, ml</i>	13.8 [8.8 – 17.3]	13.0 [9.9 – 17.6]	0.91
<i>Average HD, mm</i>	1.8 [1.3 – 2.3]		
<i>95% HD, mm</i>	4.6 [2.8 – 6.5]		

2

CardTV, cardiac target volume. All values are reported in median [IQR] See Table 1/2 for abbreviations.

1 **Table 4: Interobserver comparison using ADAS for multicenter data**

CardTV-EP volumes (n=19)	Observer 1	Observer 2	P-value
<i>Volume, ml</i>	22.0 [12.9 – 38.0]	26.0 [13.0 – 43.4]	0.08
<i>Difference in volume, ml</i>	2.1 [1.1 – 5.2]		
<i>Average HD, mm</i>	1.8 [1.5 – 2.7]		
<i>95% HD, mm</i>	5.4 [3.9 – 7.9]		

8
See Table 1/2/3 for abbreviations. All values are reported in median [IQR].

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11

12 **Table 5: Interobserver variability in multicenter STAR treated patients according to number of**
13 **mapped structures**

	All n=19	≥3 structures mapped EAM n=11	≤3 structures mapped EAM n=8	P-value
<i>Average HD, mm</i>	2.0 [1.6 – 3.1]	1.6 [1.3 – 2.0]	2.6 [1.8 – 4.1]	0.02
<i>95% HD, mm</i>	5.8 [4.1 – 8.5]	4.1 [3.6 – 5.7]	7.3 [5.3 – 11.3]	0.01

14
See Table 1/2/3 for abbreviations. All values are reported in median [IQR].

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Figure 1: Workflow duration for consecutive datasets using ADAS for an experienced and inexperienced observer

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